

Model-Based Performance Testing in the Cloud Using the MBPeT Tool

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ABSTRACT

We present an approach for performance testing of software services. We use Probabilistic Timed Automata to model the workload of the system, by describing how different user types interact with the system. We use these models to generate load in real-time and we measure different performance indicators. An in-house developed tool, MBPeT, is used to support our approach. We exemplify with an auction web service case study and show how performance information about the system under test can be collected.

Categories and Subject Descriptors

D.4.8 [Software]: performance—*measurement, modeling, monitors*

Keywords

Model-Based Performance Testing, Workload Model, Load Generation, Probabilistic Timed Automata.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of performance testing is to validate the *system under test* (SUT) in terms of responsiveness, stability, and resource utilization when it is put under a certain synthetic workload [3]. The syntectic workload should mimic the real workload as generated when real users interact with the system, as closely as possible [5]. Traditionally, the synthetic workload is generated by simulating *virtual user* (VU) behavior with scripts or pre-recorded scenarios. However, real users do not behave like static scripts. Furthermore, these scrips or scenarios can be tedious to create and maintain. Therefore, we propose an approach, supported by the MBPeT tool [1], where load is generated from abstract graphical models describing VU behavior. As such, the models are on the one hand easier to create and update, and on the other hand easier to comprehend compared to scripts, due to their abstract and graphical nature, respectively.

2. PROBABILISTIC TIMED AUTOMATA

The MBPeT tool uses models described as *probabilistic timed automata* (PTA) [4] to generate synthetic workload. A PTA consist of locations and transitions. The transitions can be labeled with three different values: a probability value, an action, and a clock. The *probability* indicates the chance

Figure 1: Example of a probabilistic timed automata

of that transition being taken. The *action* describes what action to take when the transition is fired, and the *clock* indicates how long to wait before firing the transition.

Figure 1 shows an example of a PTA describing a user profile for an online-auctioning system. Transitions have associated either a probability (e.g., 0.1) or a clock and an action to be executed. The former transitions can be used for making probabilistic choices between different paths in the graph. The later are used to send the actions corresponding to a given transition to the SUT. When a response is received, the clock is reset to zero and the next transition is fired. With the help of the probability values defined in the PTA some actions (or sequence of actions) are more likely to be chosen by MBPeT over another actions, whenever a choice is encountered in the PTA. Using PTA allows for a certain level of randomness in the generated workload which makes the later closer to the real workload.

3. MBPET TOOL

The MBPeT tool has a distributed architecture in which a master node controls and distributes the load generation on several slave nodes. Before the slaves start to generate load, the master node loads the PTA model, validates its consistency and initializes a test database with all the necessary test data, e.g., user names, password, form data, files, etc, that is needed to generate meaningful load.

The slave nodes are activated on-the-fly if more generation capacity is needed. If a slave node gets saturated, e.g., having the utilization local resources over a specified threshold, it notifies the master, while maintaining the current load capacity. The master then decides to continue load generation on another slave. The approach is especially beneficial if the slave nodes have heterogenous computation power, eliminating the need for a preliminary benchmarking process of the

different nodes.

The PTA models are used by the slave nodes for generating load in real-time against the SUT, by creating traces from the PTA models. The number of VUs on each slave is decided by the master node based on the specified ramp function. A new process is started for each VU that is going to be run concurrently. Each process simulates an independent user based on the PTA. For each simulated user, a new transition is selected in the PTA and, after waiting for the specified time, the corresponding action is sent to the system. Whenever the number of concurrent VUs has to be decreased the corresponding number of processes on each slave are just stopped.

The actions generated from the models can not, as such, directly be sent to the SUT, because the actions are abstract. Therefore, each slave node sends the abstract actions through an adapter, which can be used to either translate on-the-fly every abstract action into a machine readable format (e.g., a HTTP request) and collect the response, or to write the actions to scripts that can be executed by other tools such as JMeter [7]. The adapter acts much like a Faban Driver would in the Faban framework [6]. Faban is a tool used for development of server benchmarks and for generating workloads.

Each slave node monitors different *Key Performance Indicators* (KPIs) of the SUT, such as response time and throughput. The values are reported to the master at the end of performance test. The master node then aggregates the values reported by the slaves, calculates different different statistical indicators, and creates an HTML test report. The test report shows information of how the response time of individual actions varied over time (Figure 2), and provides plots of error rates, average throughput and network utilization, etc. If one has access to the SUT, the MBPeT tool can collect monitoring information of how resources like, CPU, memory, disk, etc, were used during the test session and include them in the test report. In our experiments, we were able to monitor the SUT and collect information using for instance the *dstats* tool which was automatically processed and include in the test report. The MBPeT tool will also present statistics of the most executed traces in the model.

Figure 2: Response times for actions plotted over time

The MBPeT tool has been built to run in a private cloud

or in a public ones, such as the Amazon EC2 cloud [2]. Since the master node does not require much computational power, it can run locally on a laptop, while the slave nodes can be set up to run in the cloud.

4. GOALS OF THE DEMONSTRATION

The goals of the demonstration is to show that using abstract models minimizes the effort of creating the workload profiles. Although the implementation the adapter requires an initial effort it can be afterwards reused without changes. Having available graphical models makes easier to visualize and change the workload profiles. With respect to load generation, using PTAs allows us to model the user profiles and generate syntectic load, via probabilistic-guided load generation, that mimics closer the real one workload. We also want to show how load is generated from the workload models and explain how the tool works. We plan to show the tool running the master node on a laptop and have the slave nodes running in the Amazon EC2 cloud. However, if it is not possible to connect properly to Amazon, we will demonstrate the tool running locally on two machines. During the demonstration we intend to show the tool in action on two different case studies, an auctioning web service and a web-based file storage service. We have done a preliminary evaluation of the MBPeT against the JMeter tool and we could conclude that for identical test configurations and load profiles, the results were similar in terms of throughput (number of actions generated per minute). We plan to briefly discuss our conclusions during the demo as well.

5. REFERENCES

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